

EPIC-WE LEGACIES

Games for Culture EXPO Catalogue

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EPIC-WE
Empowered Participants through Identifying
Cultural Worlds and Environments

Funded by
the European Union

EPIC-WE LEGACIES

Games for Culture

EXPO Catalogue

EPIC-WE Legacies: Games for Culture EXPO Catalogue

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EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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GAMES FOR CULTURE

Games for culture use game-making as a deliberate practice to explore, critique, and shape cultural values, social norms, identities, and civic imaginaries. They prioritize societal transformation, cultural dialogue, and empowerment, inviting players and creators to reflect on belonging, citizenship, and collective futures.

- **Value-driven goals:** Design is explicitly oriented toward cultural, social, or civic aims such as inclusion, identity work, or critical reflection using - in meaningful ways - the EU values.
- **Societal engagement:** Games open spaces for cultural-societal debate, empathy-building, and imagining alternative social arrangements.

- **Narrative and ethical focus:** Mechanics and stories are crafted to surface dilemmas, contested histories, and cultural narratives - highlighting EU values as a driver for change, dialogue and ethics.
- **Youth and civic empowerment:** Games for culture often aim to give underrepresented groups agency and voice in cultural-societal conversations.
- **Dialogic outcomes:** Success is evaluated by the game's ability to provoke discussion, change perspectives, or support community action.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

INTRODUCTION

Filmby Aarhus

Over the past three years, the EPIC-WE project has taken us on quite a journey. For Filmby Aarhus, it has also been an opportunity to open our doors wider—to universities, museums, and especially to young people—as part of our ambition to strengthen the games industry. What began as an ambitious idea about co-creation and youth-driven innovation has grown into a lively ecosystem of experiments, prototypes, and new perspectives on how culture, technology, and imagination meet. This Games EXPO catalogue brings together a broad selection of the “games for culture” prototypes created along the way, as well as the featured games from our three EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs in Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos.

At the heart of this project are the young creators who showed up with cultural-creative curiosity, courage, and a genuine desire to shape cultural heritage in new ways. Their energy is what has fueled EPIC-WE from day one. Without them, there would be no Cultural Game Jams, no bold ideas, and certainly no quadruple helix partnership in action. Their willingness to try, fail, rethink, and try again has inspired all of us involved in the project. We owe them a huge thank you.

The games for culture prototypes you will discover in these pages speak for themselves: they are inventive, daring, sometimes beautifully strange, and always full of personality. They reflect the different contexts of our Cultural Hubs, but also the shared spirit of collaboration that has grown between them. Each prototype represents a moment where young people, universities, cultural institutions, and creative professionals came together to build something that could only exist because all four partners were around the same table.

As we gather for the final EPIC-WE Legacies Event, we hope this Games for Culture EXPO catalogue not only showcase what EPIC-WE has produced but also highlights why Filmby Aarhus chose to be part of this journey: to amplify new and diverse voices and to help more young people find pathways into the games industry. Projects like this show what happens when we make room for youth creativity—when we trust their ideas, their values, and their ability to drive innovation in culture and society.

On behalf of Filmby Aarhus, thank you for being part of the EPIC-WE adventure and legacy. Whether you joined a Cultural Game Jam, contributed expertise, or visited our game EXPOs, your engagement has shaped this journey. And to the young people: keep creating, keep questioning, and keep playing. The future of cultural heritage and culture in all its aspects is brighter because of you, and we hope to welcome many of you again in the professional game industry.

Regitze Mai Møller, project manager in Filmby Aarhus

Ditte Brunø Søndergaard, project coordinator in Filmby Aarhus

FEATURED CULTURAL GAMES

Aarhus

Professional Development of Two Featured Games with Culture

In Aarhus Cultural Hub, the maturation of the selected games, Metamorphosis and 404 Fairness not found – the psykiosk game, followed a structured and value-driven process, combining youth engagement with professional expertise. Both titles were chosen after a collective evaluation and in-depth discussion of candidate projects, where all Aarhus Cultural Hub members prepared notes and assessments in advance.

The development of each game began with a joint start-up meeting involving industry partner Filmby Aarhus, the professional game studio Mothworks, and the participants from the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam, who made the two prototypes. These meetings created a shared framework of expectations, values, and artistic ambitions. The studio then presented detailed development proposals with clear artistic and technical steps.

Throughout the process, emphasis was placed on linking art and gameplay, ensuring that both games reflect EPIC-WE's ambition to bridge cultural and creative disciplines. This co-creation approach allowed young participants to contribute directly alongside professional developers.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

MOTHWORKS

MOTHWORKS is an independent game studio, creating unique and striking interactive experiences.

Driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition, Mothworks is gonna blow your philosophical, artsy socks off!

They got several projects in the (moth) works.

Team behind Metamorphosis

Hello, we're Puzlerne, the creators behind the core idea of Metamorphosis; the game you now see exhibited at Aros or Filmby Aarhus.

On our team we have a programmer, a storywriter, an artist and a designer, and together we strive to create games that bring people together, give new perspectives and take the world by storm!

Team behind PsyKiosk

We are 404 Fairness Not Found, a group of students at Aarhus University, united by EPIC-WE. Driven by our curiosity and a passion for design, we wanted to create something that makes players think, question, and reflect. Our game Psykiosk is the result of our shared ideas, playful experimentations, and desire to explore moral choices together.

METAMORPHOSIS

A cultural game jam project about identity, discovery, and self love.

Metamorphosis invites the player into a striking visual universe filled with playful interactions with prisms, colors, and markers of identity. The game explores themes such as freedom, identity, and self-confidence. The main character is a small bird, created by Team Puzlerne, symbolizing freedom and the struggle to find it—an image of “learning to fly,” or learning to be oneself.

The player follows the bird through five levels, each representing a step on the journey of self-discovery. Along the way, the bird encounters challenges that can only be overcome by acquiring new abilities and believing in itself. The game begins on the dark, eerie forest floor and ends at the top of a great, colorful, and radiant Tree of Life.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Puzlerne, four young people who participated in the second Cultural Game Jam in Aarhus and later matured in collaboration with the game studio Mothworks.

Mothworks is an independent game studio driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/ac83>

ART X GAME

Metamorphosis is inspired by three artworks from ARoS: Your Condensation by Olafur Eliasson, Marilyn Monroe by Andy Warhol, and House of Dionysus by Sif Itona Westerberg. These works shaped the game's themes and expression—confronting one's own reflection, how colors transform our perception of the world, and the fluidity of identity. The visual style also reflects the artworks: Warhol's color shifts appear in the aesthetics and the character's journey from grey to color, while Westerberg's sculpture inspired the Tree of Life and the ascent from forest floor to treetop.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/3cfd>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Puzlerne are Abtin Amin Marashi, Gaia Elisabeth Mikkelsen, Oliver Oak Stauenberg Orth, and Maren Valentin. They participated in 2024 in a Cultural Game Jam at ARoS in Aarhus, where they created the first prototype of Metamorphosis.

"I've attended many Game Jams before, and when I saw there was one at ARoS, I naturally wanted to join. I'm very interested in both art and games, so this Game Jam was a perfect fit for me," says Maren Valentin.

"It was a combination of my passion for game development and the chance to meet others who share the same interest as me that motivated me to take part," explains Oliver Oak.

The game studio Mothworks joined to further develop Metamorphosis in close collaboration with Team Puzlerne. Based in Aarhus, Mothworks focuses on creating unique, artistic, and eye-catching interactive experiences.

Amalie Kae, director, producer and writer at Mothworks says, *"Taking such direct inspiration from very specific cultural heritage works at ARoS has been a very interesting creative constraint, and we personally think it's made the design of Metamorphosis better."*

PsyKiosk is a point-and-click ethics adventure game that forces players to make difficult ethical choices—only to realize that no matter their actions, the end result is the same. The game provokes thought about fairness, ethics, and the illusion of choice, engaging players in a narrative where ethics is not black and white.

PsyKiosk stands out by using psychological tension in decision-making. Instead of rewarding “good” or “bad” choices, the game highlights moral ambiguity. Through aesthetic and interactive elements, the game distorts the player’s expectations, making them question their own values.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team 404, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Aarhus and the game was later matured in collaboration with the game studio Mothworks. Mothworks is an independent game studio based in Aarhus and driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition.

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/0d72>

Original prototype

FROM ART TO GAME

"Our game was strongly inspired by Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's installation Colony Howl. The mix of cultures, the almost post-apocalyptic atmosphere, and the physical feeling of walking through the space really stayed with us. Even the name PsyKiosk comes from the small kiosk in the artwork, combined with the psychedelic atmosphere we felt while exploring the installation." Says Safine Legaard Kastrupsen from the original game jam team, Team 404. The artwork reflects a dystopian, cyberpunk-inspired world that has shaped Team 404's creative vision for the PsyKiosk game.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/b904>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team 404 are Clara Bille Tvedt, Vilma Lyng Kristensen, Mads Almdal Rasmussen and Safine Legaard Kastrupsen. They participated in 2025 in a Cultural Game Jam at ARoS in Aarhus, where they created the first prototype of PsyKiosk.

"When we developed our idea, we were very focused on the theme of fairness, and on what 'fair' even really means in an unfair world. We wanted the game itself to feel unfair, so that players were pushed to reflect on their own moral choices. Is choosing the 'right' thing still morally right if it leads to a bad outcome? Does intention matter more than the result?" Says Safine.

The game studio Mothworks joined later to develop PsyKiosk further. Mothworks focuses on creating unique and artistic interactive experiences.

Anne Schulin, co-founder and art leader of Mothworks says; "The themes and moral of the original game comes through in a really effective and clever way through the gameplay, and that really excited me about Psykiosk. The core idea is super strong, and that made it fairly straight forward for us as developers to just build on top of what was already there."

FEATURED CULTURAL GAMES

Hilversum

Professional Development of Two Featured Games with Culture

At Hilversum Cultural Hub, we are working on the next step for two games: Viral Spiral and Smith and the Storm. We chose these titles because they are easy to play but also offer something to learn from. Dropstuff made an initial selection. We looked at which projects best fit our way of working: accessible, creative, and with fun as a priority. Afterwards, we presented this to the entire Cultural Hub and made the final choice.

We work in short sprints and simply try things out. Students participate from the beginning, provide feedback, help build, and contribute to improving the games. In addition, we involve other experts in our process, so we can strengthen each other. The atmosphere is open and energetic. Everyone is allowed to speak up or try things out, which makes the process lively. Sometimes things move quickly, sometimes we scrap something, but there is always movement. The games have meanwhile grown considerably: richer in content, more extensive, and simply more fun to play.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

The Creators of Immersive Arts and Interactive Experiences.

DROPSTUFF MEDIA is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences. DROPSTUFF conceptualizes, realizes and presents interactive media projects, audiovisual productions and educational programs for cultural, governmental and commercial partners.

Through exciting new experiences, DROPSTUFF MEDIA translates messages and stories to a broad audience. By applying new techniques we aim to increase public outreach and participation.

Team behind Smith and the Storm

A box of archival photos kicked off Smith and the Storm. On day one we sifted through the images, picked our favourites, and built a collage. The phrase “hotel café restaurant Smit” jumped out, so Mr. Smit became our lead and flooding our theme. We then dug into flood stories and archival visuals online, including the watersnoodramp, and shaped it into an escape room. This game was created by Gabriël Arts, Sanne Houwers, Tristan Bozarov, Duncen Krul, third-year CMD students from the Immersive Design specialisation at Utrecht University of Applied Sciences, who worked together during the 4th EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam in NL.

Team behind Viral Spiral

Viral Spiral was inspired by how quickly fake news spreads, and how important it is to spot what is real. We linked this to EU press freedom because we were curious how anyone can share news, but filtering fakes can also limit that freedom. The team included Beyzanur Aslan, Floor Pasman, Sophie More and Tim Keizer, third-year CMD students at the University of Applied Sciences Amsterdam from the Creative Research Minor, formed for the 3rd EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam in NL.

Viral Spiral

Welcome to Viral Spiral, the board game where you, as an influencer, surf through a whirlwind of real and fake news!

Your feed is overflowing with posts, but not everything can be trusted. It's up to you to separate the facts from the fakes:

Real news? Share it proudly with your followers.
Fake news? Report it... or casually swipe it away.

The better your choices, the faster you gain extra followers. Every correct move pushes you further upward, until you reach unprecedented heights.

Make the right call, keep your feed clean, climb to the top, and beat the rest.
GO VIRAL!

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team 6, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum. The game was later matured in collaboration with DROPSTUFF MEDIA. DROPSTUFF MEDIA is based in Hilversum, Netherlands and is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/e5ea>

GAME INSPIRATION

The game is inspired by a visit to The Mediamuseum in Hilversum. The students say: "We were inspired by a game focused on media manipulation and fake news and how this influences us. Seeing how media has been used as a tool for propaganda made us think about the power of news in shaping societies and the potential dangers of misinformation. This sparked the idea for Viral Spiral." The game aligns with the EU values of democracy, freedom of expression, and access to reliable information. This game serves as a tool for educating players on how misinformation spreads and the consequences of sharing it.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/aaeb>

INTERVIEW

Team 6 is Tim, Floor, Beyza and Sophie. They joined the third Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum, Netherlands in April 2024 and developed the original prototype for Viral Spiral.

When asked about the process of developing the game, the team shares: "The decision to center the game on misinformation and media literacy came from the growing relevance of these issues in today's society. By making the game interactive and challenging, we wanted players to experience the dilemma of dealing with news they might encounter online."

DROPSTUFF MEDIA joined later to further develop the game. Here they share their experience working on the game:

"The development of our game focused on creating a highly topical experience that can evolve over time. We actively involved students in the process, encouraging participation and hands-on data collection. Through continuous iteration, we refined the concept and deliberately involved external participants to generate valuable feedback and improve the overall design."

SMITH and the STORM

When the Water Returns

EPIC-WE SOUND & VISION Hogeschool van Amsterdam DROPSTUFF.nl Funded by the European Union

It is the dead of night. A raging storm lashes the coast and the water keeps rising. Hotel Smith, usually a safe haven for travelers, has become an island of stone and wood, surrounded by churning water. Roads have vanished, dikes have burst. You are trapped together with other guests, scattered across different rooms of the hotel. There is only one hope left: an old emergency transmitter at the reception desk.

Rescue services are heading out, but they don't know who is still trapped here. Only if you can work together to transmit the correct distress signal can a rescue boat reach you before the water floods the hotel. But time is running out. The transmitter is damaged. Information is scattered across different rooms. No single team has everything. Only by working together can you survive.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Orange: Gabriël Arts, Sanne Houwers, Tristan Bozarov, Duncen Krul who took part in the fourth Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum. Later, the game was further developed in collaboration with DROPSTUFF MEDIA. DROPSTUFF MEDIA is based in Hilversum, The Netherlands and is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/eade>

GAME INSPIRATION

“A box of archival photos kicked off Smith and the Storm. On day one we sifted through the images, picked our favourites, and built a collage. The phrase “hotel café restaurant Smit” jumped out, so Mr. Smit became our lead and flooding our theme. We then dug into flood stories and archival visuals online, including the watersnoodramp, and shaped it into an escape room,” says Team Orange.

The game incorporates the value of human dignity, as the game is about cooperation between different people even in scary situations. The game focuses on the importance of helping others despite the subtle differences between us.

INTERVIEW

Team Orange joined the fourth Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum, The Netherlands in September 2025 and developed the original prototype for Smith and the Storm.

Here they share the process of developing the prototype:

“Our prototype exists out of a maquette of the entire escape room and a few puzzles to showcase what you would do inside the escape room. We decided to make a maquette of the escape room, to show our vision of how we wanted it to look if we were to ever turn this into a real escape room.”

The game studio DROPSTUFF MEDIA joined later to further develop the game.

When asked about their experience of working on the game, they say:

“Our design process focused on making cultural heritage relevant in a contemporary context. The initial ideas and direction were largely driven by students, which we then built upon and further developed. A key challenge was translating these ideas into an engaging game design. Throughout the process, young creators were involved and provided valuable feedback that helped shape and refine the final concept.”

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/6258>

FEATURED CULTURAL GAMES

Óbidos

Professional Development of Four Featured Games with Culture

At Óbidos Cultural Hub, the selection of the two games to be matured (Puss in Books and Criminal Fauna Identification) happened after the second game jam, so that there was a fair amount of time to improve them. The selection process included every Cultural Hub partner, including youth, so that the selected games made sense from every partner's perspective. They should be fun, creative, and culturally relevant/informative, while having direct or indirect commercial potential.

However, some of the games that resulted from the third game jam were acclaimed in those same respects, and there was a feeling of missed opportunity for not including them in the selection. After some analysis by the Cultural Hub's CI partner, BATTLESHEEP, it was decided that two more games could move forward with the maturing process, adding Blue Brigade and Bufo Catcher to the lot.

Given the relatively high quality of the four selected games, BATTLESHEEP decided to enquire the original authors if they would like to be involved in the maturing process, working as game designers, programmers, artists, and audio producers, while receiving professional support and following industry practices. Every participant enthusiastically agreed, as it gave them an opportunity to remain attached to their creations while evolving professionally.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

BATTLESHEEP is a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, focused on both independent and work-for-hire projects.

Founded as a side-project in 2008 by a team of industry professionals with multi-platform experience, it quickly evolved into an established game studio.

We have released mobile and browser games, ranging from single-player to online multiplayer experiences.

We started out developing casual and advergaming for clients, while simultaneously publishing our own original titles.

More recently we have been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Team behind Blue Brigade

Our jam team was named “Ovo Escalfado” (Poached Egg). A very diverse group of people, each with their specialty. Artists (Daniel Fernandes and Gabriela Branco), programmers (António Rodrigues and Tomás Franco), a concept artist (Lorena Bueno), and a sound designer (Tiago Lourenço).

Team behind Criminal Feather Identification

Hi there! The original team for C.F.I. is made up of a small group of first year students in Lusofona’s Videogames bachelor’s, both artists and programmers, brought together during the second EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam at Óbidos. Our group included Júlia Costa, João Nogueira, Gabriela Branco, Afonso Cunha, Mariana Martins and António Rodrigues.

Team behind Puss In Books

Hey! We are team “Ovo Cozido” (Boiled Egg) and we created the game Puss in Books! On our team we have just 2 people, a programmer (António) and an artist (Gabriela). Together we love making games and participating in game jams!

Team behind Mole Catcher

Hello! We are “Ovo Estrelado” (Fried Egg), the team behind Mole Catcher. We are composed of a programmer, a pixel artist, and a game designer/pixel character artist, although we all shared some of the game design tasks. We came together by chance and have been working on other projects together since!

Blue Brigade is a small game made by six people, where you play as a PIDE agent during the Portuguese restricting regime, in the town of Óbidos and armed with the regime's iconic blue pencil. At first, it feels light and playful as you run around censoring people who break the rules.

But as you notice the banned clothes, forbidden music, and silenced conversations, the tone shifts, and the village begins to lose its colors. Behind the cute art and simple tasks, the game quietly shows the weight of living under censorship.

GAME CREATORS

The game was originally created by Team Ovo Escalfado, six young people who participated in the third Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos and it was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/cca6>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Ovo Escalfado (Poached Egg) are Daniel Fernandes, Gabriela Branco, António Rodrigues, Tomás Franco, Lorena Bueno and Tiago Lourenço. When asked about the experience Daniel says: *“An exciting teamwork project that allowed us to develop a remarkable game while also learning a lot about Óbidos’ culture and history.”*

“A funny and at times stressful project that really pushed our creativity, with stretchy character animations that gave the whole game a unique, quirky charm,” explains António.

“A cute and ironic art style packed with earthy tones, sketchy line art, and round characters that make up for the realistic historic time and tough situation it presents,” says Lorena.

The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop the game. Nélío Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: *“It’s incredible that a game with this depth and charm was the product of a game jam. It is challenging and fun to play, it looks amazing, and has layers of details that you unveil only through multiple playthroughs.”*

GAME INSPIRATION

When the theme of the game jam was announced, the Carnation Revolution of 1974, a lot of ideas immediately came to mind. A knight wielding a black censor bar and hitting people with it to censor them. As the theme was explored more closely and the historical context was examined, the ideas shifted toward something more authentic. Instead of a censor bar, the tool actually used at the time, the blue pencil, was introduced, making it fitting for the player to take the role of an agent from that era. Further research into the period revealed what people were forbidden to talk about, the clothing styles that were banned, and the music and books that were censored.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/78f7>

In Puss In Books, you embark on a journey guiding a kitty through a whimsical journey as it explores dreams inspired by Óbidos' legends. Traverse a literary world and craft an enchanting narrative as the cat travels through the captivating scenarios within its dreams.

Experience a blend of imagination and adventure, where each dream unveils new challenges and discoveries in a quest to uncover the essence of literary magic. With this game, we hope to offer a small taste of Óbidos through typography, books, and hopefully cats!

GAME CREATORS

The original prototype game was created by Team Ovo Cozido, two young people who took part in the first Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos, in February 2024. Puss In Books was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/3f96>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Ovo Cozido are António Rodrigues, a programmer, and Gabriela Branco, an artist. They participated in 2024 in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos under the theme “Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature,” where they created the first prototype of Puss In Books.

When asked about the experience António says: *“It was a lot of fun to work on and to visit the town and to make a small cozy game about a cat living through stories.”*

Gabriela continues, *“Óbidos was an inspiring experience we will carry for life.”*

The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop Puss In Books. BATTLESHEEP have released mobile and browser games, ranging from single-player to online multiplayer experiences. Nélío Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: *“Living proof of what a small, talented team can accomplish in a very short time with the right focus. Being so content-heavy, this was a risky project to do in a game jam context. Yet here it is for everyone to experience.”*

GAME INSPIRATION

The game takes inspiration from Scribblenauts and the way its puzzles interact with the environment around the player. The idea came from an excursion trip to Óbidos, where a visit to a typography shop included an introduction to the craft of printing and the process of imprinting shapes and letters onto paper. This inspired the idea for a writing game. While strolling around Óbidos and seeing kitty after kitty in the streets, lying in stores and at libraries, the main character had to be a kitty. The current version of the game took inspiration from the Óbidos legend "Door of Betrayal".

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/e9a2>

In the Óbidos Lagoon, several crimes occur throughout the year. From stealing someone's precious items to well-prepared murder scenes. The culprits? Birds! Play as a detective and find out who did the atrocities in the case files. Arrest those feathery criminals and earn yourself a promotion!

This game was made with the objective of offering, through some ridiculous designs and laidback aesthetics, a way to teach or promote interest in the lagoon's fauna and other dynamics within this ecosystem.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Júlia Costa, João Nogueira, Gabriela Branco, Afonso Cunha, Mariana Martins and António Rodrigues. Six young people who participated in the second Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos. The game was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

YOU WERE WRONG.

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/d37b>

INTERVIEW

The team behind Criminal Feather Identification participated in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos in 2024, where they created the first prototype originally called Criminal Fauna Identification. When asked about the process of developing the game the team says: *“The Óbidos Game Jam was an unforgettable experience! Turning birds into characters was an interesting adventure, making them look somewhat resembling a criminal while keeping them true to their living counterparts was a captivating challenge,”* says João. Mariana continues, *“The jam was an experience that I wouldn't have the opportunity to have at any other time. I was inexperienced then, but participating pushed me and helped me build a habit to keep creating. I felt much more confident in my skills, which enabled me to have fun finishing this project.”* The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop the game. *“A lot of research went into this game, with the team pushing hard to keep it playful, funny, informative, and replayable. The true meaning of team effort and dedication,”* says Nélio Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP.

GAME INSPIRATION

The main inspiration was a game called “Time Waster”, where you have to connect simplified crime descriptions to mugshots of human criminals. The theme of the Cultural Game Jam was “Óbidos Lagoon”, and who better represents it than its residents, the avifauna? In the game, all the criminals are native birds from the Óbidos Lagoon. Following their habits and lifestyle, they perform crimes inspired by their way of living and eating habits. All suspects in the game were kept as birds to make it harder to dismiss the innocent ones. The game “Papers, Please” was also an inspiration, in the way the information is presented to the player through different files.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/47e9>

Mole Catcher

You are transported back to 1974 Portugal, which is under the regime of a dictatorship. You are stationed in the small town of Óbidos as a revolutionary tasked with keeping check of who enters the village's iconic theatre, which is home to a crucial meeting for the upcoming revolution, meant to overthrow the dictatorship!

However, you are informed that moles are trying to infiltrate the meeting. It is your job to check documents and compare information to find out who the moles are!

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Ovo Estrelado, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos. Behind Team Ovo Estrelado are Cátia Nascimento, Maria Sequeira, Júlia Costa and Tiago Lourenço. Mole Catcher was later matured in collaboration with the game studio BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/8623>

INTERVIEW

Team Ovo Estrelado participated in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos in 2025, where they created the first prototype of Mole Catcher, originally called Bufo Catcher. When asked about the process of developing the game the team says: “Everything in the playable area was idealized with the intent of making the player feel like they were truly living that role of a guard in 1974,” says Cátia. “To truly immerse the player, we tried our best to find real-life information that was used at the time,” says Maria. “We wanted to convey to the player the sense of secrecy and fear the Portuguese people faced during the harsh years of the Estado Novo,” Júlia says. “The worry of being constantly watched and spied on and that every action you took might get judged by an authority and even get you arrested.” Later in the process the game studio BATTLESHEEP joined to further develop the game. Nélio Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: “Disguised as a simple game, this is a true gem of an idea. Shedding light on true events, it particularly speaks to the hearts of those who lived through the Portuguese regime and, later, the revolution.”

GAME INSPIRATION

The theme behind the Cultural Game Jam was the Portuguese Carnation Revolution and the jam took place in the town of Óbidos. That was a good opportunity to make the game be set in the town and highlight this aspect of the preparations for the revolution that has been overshadowed and is widely unknown. The main inspiration was the game “Papers, Please”, as that was the best format to show military artifacts and objects of that time and the grime and overwhelming pressure that was felt during the dictatorship. “Small nods to the time in which the game took place, were the artistic choices in things like, for example, the character sprites, whose artistic direction was inspired by the colors and proportions used by famous Portuguese painters who lived through the dictatorship,” says Maria Sequeira.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/3288>

INTRODUCTION

THE CULTURAL GAME PROTOTYPES

During the EPIC-WE project we have hosted **12 Cultural Game Jams** - 4 from the Óbidos Cultural Hub in Portugal, 4 from the Hilversum Cultural Hub in the Netherlands, and 4 from the Aarhus Cultural Hub in Denmark.

Here, **424 young people** (between 15-25) have worked together in teams to create **108 Cultural Game Prototypes**. Either as **games through culture** - working directly with culture as material for game-making - or as **games for culture** - exploring or interpreting heritage and values through game-making that aim for critical reflection, civic engagement, or cultural transformation.

From these cultural game prototypes each Cultural Hub selected two or more of the teams games to be further developed into a featured **game with culture** through close collaboration between youth and the three Cultural Hub's game studios - showing how games working with culture can play a role in co-creating new futures in the intersection of games, heritage, values, and culture. In total **8 Featured EPIC-WE Games** was developed during the project.

For the EPIC-WE Legacies Event a broad selection of the 108 Cultural Game Prototypes has been curated by each Cultural Hub to be showcased at ARoS Art Museum and Filmby Aarhus as one of the big legacies of the project. For the Games through Culture EXPO at ARoS Art Museum, 18 games were selected and showcased and for the Games for Culture EXPO at Filmby Aarhus, 20 games were selected and showcased.

This is the legacy of young people taking up game-making as a form of culture-making - the result of which you find in this EXPO Catalogue. The EXPO Catalogue contains and presents all the showcased Cultural Game Prototypes along with the 8 Featured Games. Together they illustrate the power of young people's cultural-creative thinking with heritage and values and the potential of Cultural Game Jams inviting young people to game jam with cultural heritage themes, sites, collections, archives, artworks, values, and identities.

In this catalogue we celebrate all of the young people that is the beating and empowered heart of our epic-we - we hope they inspire you like they have inspired us!

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

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APHASIA

Created by: Alexander, Aran, Hazel, Jakob and Oscar
Building on: Human dignity and freedom
Inspired by: Christian Lemmerz' sculpture 'Aphasia II' (1986)

Explore repetitive life and human dignity.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/3d49>

Reflect on mundane routines and discover what makes life worthwhile. 'Aphasia' examines the repetitive nature of life and questions human dignity and freedom. The player experiences a cycle of everyday tasks that blur reality. We want the players to reflect on their own life, to think about what parts of their life are most meaningful.

US & THEM

Created by: Hannah, Kasper, Tobias and Frederik
Building on: Human dignity
Inspired by: James Turrell's 'Milkrun III' (2002) and Pipilotti Rist's 'Dawn Hours in the Neighbour's House' (2005)

Will you survive the night?

Backstory

You have been busy lately at your crappy corporate day-time job. You have been procrastinating your house chores for long enough. So you decide that you going to pull an all nighter to get them done.

The landlord just called you to inform you that someone new is to move into the adjacent empty apartment in a week or so. The landlord seems slightly off, and quickly ends the call.

You think nothing of it, and make your way to your apartment complex. You spot some weird looking boxes sitting outside the hallway.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/a3db>

Survive the night, as you help the main character completing his household chores and fulfilling his basic needs while spying on the neighbor. The game explores neighborhood and paranoia in an eerie, unsettling atmosphere that distorts reality. Through horror, the game highlights the discomfort of villainizing or "othering" the neighbor.

KNOW YOUR NEIGHBOR(?)

Created by: Petra, Ingrid, Alma, Nicoline and Astrid
Building on: Equality
Inspired by: Pippilotti Rist's installation 'Dawn Hours in the Neighbour's House' (2005)

Are you aware of your own prejudices?

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/7c7e>

In this puzzle game players are told to identify objects that don't belong in a Danish apartment. The game explores equality, prejudice, and how culture is shared across society through unconscious biases, passed down from generation to generation. Our hope is for players to be aware of their own prejudices as well as to encourage dialog.

CENSORED TRUTHS

Created by: Alessandro Trotta, Simone Micalizzi and Louis Godtfred Kastrop Lindgaard
Building on: Freedom and rule of law
Inspired by: Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Århus 31 May 1849' (1853)

For whom do you decide to speak?

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/7426>

An augmented reality simulation in which you're a press worker in the authoritarian republic of Naşúl. Choose what to print for an underground newsletter: will you align with the regime, or do you dare to reveal buried truths? Your choices affect public sentiment and may or may not create room for critical thinking and change.

CULTURAL GAME JAMS AARHUS

CULTURAL GAME JAMS AARHUS

A WEEK OF WAR

Created by: Sigrid, Evian and Julie

Building on: Democracy

Inspired by: Inspired by: Olafur Eliasson's 'Your Rainbow Panorama' (2011) and James Turrell's 'Milkrun III' (2002)

Democracy is suspended, every choice is yours alone.

Step into the role of Denmark's supreme leader for a week of war. You have seven days to secure power and stabilize the nation. Democracy is suspended; every choice is yours alone. Will you lead your people with freedom or dominate with force? Your legacy depends on how far you're willing to go. In the end, power is the price of survival.

SEND ANOTHER CREW

Created by: Kalle, Christian, Jonas, Mille and Jonas

Building on: Human dignity

Inspired by: Pippilotti Rist's 'Dawn Hours in the Neighbour's House' (2005) and Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's 'Colony Howl' (2022)

You pray to your gods that it all goes smoothly.

The year is 2125. It is your first day as a mechanics assistant on board a submarine, owned by Big Gordon Corp. You are on a mission to a city flooded by rising sea levels, to deliver some cargo. Sail through the dark waters of a dystopian future, while experiencing the consequences of an unequal power hierarchy.

BLISS

Created by: Leonard Hjuler Baungaard, Maya Stuckert, Emilie Lykkegaard Schmidt and Patrizia Bjertrup-Röben

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Vilhelm Kyhn's painting 'View at Vejle Fjord' (1862)

Escape to nature and balance resources.

Escape to nature and balance resources in this anti-expansionist game. "Bliss" is about escaping modern society to live in balance with nature. Manage resources wisely as the expansion comes with a price. Collect resources in a forest, with the environment reacting to your actions.

THE GAME OF INFLUENCE

Created by: Sofie Østerby Spielberg, Florentina Bujupai, Evelyn Denise Lencina Rosales and Sofie Bredahl

Building on: Human dignity, equality and freedom

Inspired by: Olafur Eliasson's 'Your Rainbow Panorama' (2011), James Turrell's 'Milkrun III' (2002) and Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's 'Colony Howl' (2022)

Confront invisible forces that govern social life.

Players are dropped into a social simulation, where every choice they make affects their inclusion or exclusion from a group. Assigned a random identity – complete with background, income, and beliefs – they must navigate a judgmental dinner party setting, uncovering how social bias, privilege, and unspoken norms shape who gets to belong.

FLIPPER FRONT

Created by: Team 3

Building on: Rule of law

Inspired by: Climate change impact

Seals fight for survival in the North Sea.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/3a66>

A cooperative boardgame where seals fight for survival in a future Netherlands. Rising seas open new habitats while government, dikes, islands, and laws stand in their way. Seals try to protect the North Sea in a dystopian world where the government starts expanding into their waters.

FLASH FLOOD

Created by: Team Flash Flood

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Dutch flood disasters

Fields are sinking under water, and your animals are in danger!

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/ffb6>

You are a farmer in the Netherlands. Every day your animals – cows, horses, sheep and chickens – graze peacefully in the fields. Earth is getting warmer. High in the Alps, the ice and snow are melting increasingly faster. It's up to you to rescue them. Only the smartest and bravest farmer will succeed in saving the animals.

WET FEET

Created by: Team Mean Girls
Building on: Equality and democracy
Inspired by: Extreme weather events due to climate change

Do you only think of yourself, or will you help build a future where everyone stays dry and alive.

The water level is rising, and not everyone is facing the same challenges. Some live high and safe, others low and vulnerable. Yet, everyone is dependent on each other. Only through support and cooperation will the entire polder remain dry. But will you stick your neck out and help others, even if it costs you land or resources?

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/596b>

MEESTROMEN

Created by: Team Express
Building on: Human dignity and democracy
Inspired by: Stills from the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Save your own land from flooding and/or help someone else from the same fate.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/fc89>

This quick boardgame will let you manage your own 'waterschap'. Will you act fast enough to prevent your waterschap from flowing over with water and will you help others save theirs? The Netherlands has a long history of the dangers of the water that surrounds the small country. Protect the country from these dangers!

CULTURAL GAME JAMS HILVERSUM

CULTURAL GAME JAMS HILVERSUM

GENERATION PLASTIC SOUP

Created by: Team The Riff

Building on: Equality and rule of law

Inspired by: The pictures in the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

The old vs the new generation are battling for their own agenda.

This game is about plastic polluting the ocean and how different generations are looking at this so-called 'plastic soup'. We have rights to have clean water, but tension between generations, values, and visions of the future confronts the player with difficult dilemmas. How can we find solutions where we're all treated like equals?

TERRA MATER

Created by: Team Terra Mater

Building on: Human dignity

Inspired by: Archivematerials about the Watersnoodramp in 1953 from the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

No one knows what lies ahead, but all must climb if they wish to see tomorrow.

The dams holding the water out of the mountainside broke. The water is rising at an alarming rate. Villages become unlivable, forests vanish and familiar places are disappearing. Yet life endures. Humans carry stories of their ancestors, while animals guard the memory of the wild. You must spin the wheel and reach into the bag of fate.

ÓBIDOS WATCH

Created by: António Rodrigues, Afonso Cunha, Eduardo Rocha, Gabriela Branco and Júlia Costa
Building on: Rule of law and life on land
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem

Document new species and identify littering tourists while keeping detailed records of offenses.

Photograph new species while ensuring the protection of bird habitats by removing barking dogs. Identify and capture photo evidence of tourists littering or trespassing, meticulously recording offenses. Engage in vigilant observation and documentation to preserve the natural environment and promote responsible tourism practices in Óbidos.

OTTERWAY

Created by: José Reis, Madalena Cagido and Tiago Berlim
Building on: Rule of law, life below water
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem

Help the otter clean the Óbidos Lagoon while managing its survival needs.

OtterWay is a survival game where you play as an otter trying to clean the Óbidos Lagoon, however you must manage your hunger and oxygen levels. There are two types of trash: plastic/metal and glass. You must put the trash in the respective bin in order to get points. There are also fishermen trying to catch you with nets.

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CULTURAL GAME JAMS ÓBIDOS

CULTURAL GAME JAMS ÓBIDOS

STORYTELLER

Created by: Paulo Silva, Daniel Costa, Ivan Emidio, Mariana Martins, João Nogueira, Dinis Ferreira and Bruno Alegria

Building on: Freedom and democracy

Inspired by: The town of Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature

Replace fake books with real ones to preserve Óbidos' cultural heritage.

Access the game <https://lnk.dk/ec82>

In 20th century Óbidos, during the Estado Novo regime, a man discovers the city walls being rebuilt with fake books by Salazar's orders. Determined to preserve literary culture, he embarks on a quest to find uncensored books and replace the fake ones, safeguarding the integrity of knowledge and freedom of expression.

SPIRIT OF THE LAKE

Created by: Gonçalo Sampaio, Leonardo Henrique, Tomás Cardoso, Hugo Silva, Inês Gomes and Eduardo Rocha

Building on: Life on land and below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem

Roam the Óbidos Lagoon as a fox spirit, ensuring nature's balance.

Access the game <https://lnk.dk/ab03>

A fox was possessed by the spirit of the lake. Now, in this new body, the spirit roams around the Óbidos Lagoon to check if the animals and their habitats are according to the Nature regulations.

BLOOMING SHALLOWS

Created by: David Mendes, Ricardo Louro, Daniel Fernandes and Vasco Caleiro
Building on: Sustainability
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem

Build your village while maintaining ecological balance.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/d3b2>

Face the task of constructing and expanding your village while maintaining a delicate balance in resource consumption to preserve the surrounding ecosystem. Strategically manage materials to foster sustainable growth and overcome environmental challenges, ensuring the prosperity and harmony of your evolving community within the serene Shallows.

BIRDIPEDIA

Created by: Luan Velho, Pedro Batista and Daniela Sousa
Building on: Life on land and below water
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem

Preserve bird species in the Óbidos Lagoon in an unconventional manner.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/a090>

Living in the Óbidos Lagoon, an old lady and her pet, Lucas, an octopus, are constantly in fear that the birds that live near them will someday disappear. So they took it upon themselves not to let it happen. By buying a bazooka that can shoot Lucas without harming him so that he can catch the birds to collect, study and preserve them.

EPIC-WE CULTURAL GAME JAMS

Empowering Innovation: Living Labs and Youth Participation

Interview with Dimitri Schuurman

Expert Member of EPIC-
WE Advisory Board

Visiting Professor Gent University – Business Developer imec-MICT-UGent – Senior Research Strategist ENoLL. Dimitri Schuurman is an expert in Living Labs, innovation management, co-creation, co-design, and user innovation, particularly in the context of emerging technologies.

EPIC-WE have seen the full inclusion of our Youth Advisory Members into decision-making and creation processes. Does this integration of Youth align with the envisioned multi-stakeholder model of Living Labs?

By involving Youth on an organisational level, the project is taking an important step forward. One key consideration is the extent to which the Youth members will be involved: will they be motivated to shape the strategic direction of the project, or will they be more interested in short-term participation?, he asks. Regardless, the approach is innovative, whether it succeeds or faces challenges, as the insights can benefit future initiatives.

And does it have the potential to enhance the project's impact?

Undoubtedly. It is essential that Youth members have a seat at the table, are treated equally, and have an equal voice in decision-making. Their motivation to stay involved can be seen as a key indicator of whether true empowerment has

been achieved. In this sense, disengagement would have to lead to reassessment of the approach, to understand what changes are needed to ensure everyone feels valued and included in EPIC-WE.

EPIC-WE is committed to cross-sectoral collaborations, and so, the project welcomes strategies for more unified and synergistic approaches. Are there any strategies or insights of special relevance?

One effective strategy he highlights is organising offline events where participants are grouped into multidisciplinary teams and given tasks or discussion topics in a playful and engaging environment. Another effective method can be to use design-based approaches, in which groups work together to create something tangible. Providing participants with alternative ways to express themselves (such as through drawing, building, or designing) can foster mutual understanding and ensure that everyone contributes.

“When working with Youth members, their role changes drastically when they are referred to as “experts on the needs and wants of Youth”, instead of simply ‘young people’.”

Ethical Youth Engagement in EPIC-WE

Interview with Stig Børsen Hansen

Expert member of EPIC-
WE Advisory Board

Stig Børsen Hansen is the external ethics advisor to EPIC-WE. Hansen brings invaluable expertise, helping us in our commitment as well as practice to involve young people in a recognised and fair manner throughout EPIC-WE.

A balancing act: 'codified' and 'experiential' ethics

"Teaching ethics involves navigating two distinct dimensions," Hansen explains. "Firstly, there are the codifiable aspects: informed consent, security of data, clear communication, and intellectual property rights. These can, and should be, explicitly taught." However, ethics go far beyond the 'codifiable'. There is a less tangible dimension that is crucial here, which is more "fine-grained and experiential" but it is just as important as the more straightforward elements in ethical practices.

Ethical considerations in youth engagement

"Young people, especially teenagers, can and should have a say in consent processes." His main advice on this is to ensure that communication is clear, and always in dialogue, and also to be conscious of understanding and respecting young people's capabilities.

Creating spaces for genuine expression

To ethically involve youth, Hansen recommends establishing conditions that are conducive for authentic feedback and expression. "It's important to have forums where young people can freely express their thoughts, including subversive or playful feedback," he suggests. Hansen emphasises paying close attention to youth voices and behaviours that may indicate dissent, boredom, or disagreement, as these can provide valuable insights into ethical engagement and reflection.

Recognition and fairness as cornerstones

While researchers and institutions are getting something they need from the interact with young participants, we should also ask: "Are youths getting something valuable out of this engagement, such as professional networks, academic credits, or certificates?" and he adds that we should be genuinely open to their own ideas about what they could get out of their participation.

"Being ethical researchers means continually adjusting our practices through reflection and open conversation. By genuinely listening to and respecting young people, EPIC-WE can ensure ethical integrity and meaningful participation."

Designing for Values

Interview with Mary Flanagan

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

A game designer, researcher, artist, and founder of Tiltfactor Lab at Dartmouth College, Mary is a pioneer in value-centred game design. As a member of our Advisory Board, she continues to help us explore how values and culture can intersect meaningfully through game-making.

More Than Just a Game: Putting Values at the Center

Flanagan's work revolves around a simple yet transformative idea: games are cultural artifacts. And as such, they express values. *"The important thing,"* Flanagan explains, *"is that values don't have to be abstract. We can treat them like design challenges. What does caring look like in a game? What does freedom of expression mean as a mechanic? These become starting points for creativity."*

Making Cultural Values Tangible

While values are often easy to discuss, culture can be more elusive, especially when the goal is to create games that express shared European identities or heritage. *"It's hard to talk about 'culture' without drifting into abstraction. That's why facilitators need tools, examples, and ways to ground the conversation."* Start with real cultural references and encourage participants to remix them by modifying a known game imagining a new one, or drawing storyboards.

Centering the Process, Not Just the Product

A recurring theme in Mary's work, and a core value of EPIC-WE, is the importance of the process. In value-based game design, it's not about shipping a flawless game. It's about what happens along the way: the conversations, the decisions, the reflections. *"Community, values, and ideation are central to the process,"* she explains. *"It's critical that your evaluation captures that – not just the game at the end."*

Designing for Empowerment and Agency

Beyond cultural values and inclusivity, EPIC-WE also aims to nurture a sense of agency in young participants. Flanagan believes game-making is uniquely positioned to do just that. *"Game creation gives people the chance to shape systems, make choices, and tell their own stories,"* she says. But it must be approached thoughtfully. Her advice: make sure everyone has a meaningful role. Offer collaborative challenges with no single "winner."

"Think about what you want the experience to feel like. How do you want participants to see themselves afterward? That's where empowerment begins."

Creativity, Community, and the Power of Process

Interview with Anneke Van Woerden

Expert Member of EPIC-WE Advisory Board

With a background that bridges cultural studies, experience design, and social innovation, Anneke brings deep insight into community-based creative processes. Her leadership in initiatives like the Global Goals Jam, and her expertise in learning and facilitation, make her a vital contributor to our shared mission.

The Process Over the Prototype

One of Anneke's key insights is a shift in mindset: from product to process. *"In the early days, we were focused on outcomes — on building something tangible by the end of a jam. But over time, we realized the real magic happens in the collaboration itself,"* she says. *"The conversations, the negotiations, the collective understanding of a challenge — that's where change starts."*

Creating Space for Creativity for everyone

"Creativity flourishes when people feel seen and heard. That's why trust-building, even if it feels like a soft skill, is essential." She also pushes back against narrow ideas of creativity: *"Brainstorming sessions can be great, but they often favour extroverts. We need to embrace a diversity of methods — visual, written, silent reflection — to make sure everyone's voice is heard."*

Embracing Diversity—Locally and Globally

EPIC-WE's Cultural Hubs each approach European values through different lenses. Anneke sees this as a strength. *"When you allow each hub to lean into its unique context, surprising commonalities emerge,"* she notes. *"Sometimes it's by starting local that you end up discovering shared values."* She adds: *"We offered a framework, but local hosts are the experts of their context. That's where the magic happens."*

Human Connection as the Core

Throughout the conversation, Anneke returns again and again to one central theme: human connection. *"At the start of building the GGJ community, I spent hours on one-on-one calls. That personal connection laid the groundwork for everything,"* she says. *"Even as we scaled, we tried to keep that sense of closeness — through local ambassadors, annual webinars, or sharing stories from past jams."*

"Don't underestimate the power of coming together—with trust, creativity, and the courage to ask better questions."

The power of helical frameworks

Interview with Elias Carayannis

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

Dr. Elias G. Carayannis is a Full Professor of Science, Technology, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship at The George Washington University School of Business. In 2009-10 he co-created the Quadruple Helix concept and later expanded it to the Quintuple Helix, incorporating environmental sustainability to drive growth and resilience.

How has the quadruple helix evolved, and what does it mean for current projects like EPIC-WE?

Since the '90s, there has been an emphasis on fostering public-private partnerships for research and technology advancement. The triple helix concept emerged, focusing on collaboration among governments, universities, and industries. However, this model primarily benefitted elites, leaving out broader societal participation. This imbalance led me to develop the quadruple helix, which adds civil society to the equation, ensuring that innovation and resource allocation include a wider array of voices and perspectives. The quadruple helix model incorporates civil society, ensuring transparency, representation, and empowerment for all individuals, especially those directly impacted by environmental issues.

What challenges have you encountered in fostering collaboration across diverse stakeholder groups?

Effective collaboration often faces challenges due to diverse expertise and perspectives. For examples, in a UN project on intangible cultural heritage, diverse backgrounds led to communication barriers and misalignment. This highlighted the need for a shared language and common understanding. I coined the paradox of converging disciplines and diverging specializations to describe this. It's critical to use mixed methods—qualitative and quantitative—to develop a shared language of thought.

How can we integrate youth into the quadruple helix framework effectively?

Youth are a vital part of civil society, bringing unique perspectives and longer time horizons. Engaging them requires understanding their thoughts, aspirations, fears, and expectations. It's essential to build consensus and involve them in co-creating a shared vision. Projects like EPIC-WE need to cultivate a common language that resonates with both older and younger generations, fostering unity and collaboration.

“In essence, our goal is to foster an environment where all stakeholders are co-creators, actively engaged in shaping the outcome. This approach ensures that our initiatives are not only effective but also sustainable and inclusive.”

Giving youth the power to shape culture

Interview with Inês Nunes

Expert Member of EPIC-WE Youth Advisory Board

Inês Nunes is a student and researcher in neuropsychology and communication sciences, specialising in serious games for rehabilitation. She brings a critical perspective to EPIC-WE's mission of empowering young Europeans to shape culture through imagination, game design, and cultural heritage.

Cultural Game Jams: acts of encounter and (re)discovering

The Cultural Game Jams lie at the heart of EPIC-WE, it is where safe spaces are created for young people to reinterpret local and European heritage through game-making. Inês points to the transformative potential of the game jams, and how they have revealed hidden or forgotten layers of familiar as well as unfamiliar heritage. *“Sometimes it feels like we’re rediscovering our own culture. The themes—like the Óbidos Lagoon or the 25th of April Revolution—have given us the freedom to be creative, to reflect on the past, and to connect it to our future.”*

Learning by leading: giving up control

As a facilitator in the game jams, Inês became very much aware of the delicate balance between guiding and influencing, especially when working with youth: *“It’s always a concern—so you need to ask yourself: am I forcing a perspective?”*

she explains, *“I prefer letting participants explore the theme from their own point of view.”*

Inspiring tangible impact in local communities

Inês sees clear signs that EPIC-WE is making a lasting difference in her community. From learning about endangered professions like traditional booksellers to discovering that the Óbidos lagoon is a UNESCO property, the project has sparked real-world engagement. *“Young people started to realise that their actions have an impact. We’re not just preserving culture—we’re living it.”* And when the game jam explored the 25th of April, Portugal’s Freedom Day, it prompted profound reflection on active citizenship, democracy and human rights. *“We have to make sure our actions today keep us from going back to the past. That’s the power of this project—it connects the past, present, and future.”*

“Try. We all have something to say. At the very least, you’ll find someone willing to listen to your story.”

Aspects of game creation

Interview with Gaetano Dimita

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

Gaetano Dimita is a Reader in Interactive Entertainment and Intellectual Property (IP) Law at the Centre for Commercial Law Studies (CCLS), Queen Mary University of London. Gaetano contributes to EPIC-WE by exploring how legal frameworks influence game creation and gameplay experiences.

How has the video game industry approached supporting community creativity, and what legal challenges do creators face in monetizing and protecting their work?

The video game industry has been relatively proactive in supporting community creativity compared to other industries. Over time, user license agreements evolved, with some offering broad freedoms for creative works as long as they adhered to certain guidelines. Others are much stricter, claiming ownership over user creations or requiring perpetual, royalty-free licenses for any derivative works. This uncertainty extends to modern platforms like YouTube and Twitch, where creators build livelihoods through “let’s play” videos or streams. Many digital creators do not fully understand the implications of their actions or how to safeguard their creative output.

How can we empower creators with the right tools and knowledge from the very beginning of a Cultural Game Jam?

During Cultural Game Jams, creators should learn how licenses define usage rights—whether the license is perpetual, global, or restricted—and that they retain moral rights even after licensing. For instance, they can object if someone alters their work in ways that violate its integrity or removes their name as the creator. These are fundamental principles, and while creators don’t need to master every legal detail, they should grasp the basics to protect their creations.

How can creators navigate the complexities of intellectual property, contracts, and profit sharing to ensure fair compensation and long-term success?

Divide the roles and document it: It’s important to recognize that there are different roles and expertise required when scaling a project, and no one person can master everything.

Know when to call a lawyer and know it can be free: These considerations also depend on the type of contract the creators have. Having legal counsel during negotiations is invaluable.

“If we want to build a sustainable creative economy, it is essential to educate creators on their copyright and legal rights, so that they can protect and monetize their work effectively.”

Imagination in Motion:

What can a game teach us about ourselves?

Interview with Chris Solarski

Expert Member of EPIC-
WE Advisory Board

Chris Solarski, a game designer, artist, and educator, about this and other topics. His work combines movement, storytelling, and visual design. In addition, Solarski is an important member of the EPIC-WE project as part of the project's Advisory Board

From Michelangelo to Mario

Solarski's story started in game development, working as an artist at Sony, but he soon found himself pulled toward other forms of art, including figurative drawing, gesture, and the emotional weight of form. He began exploring how the principles of painting and sculpture could shape not only the visuals of games but also their design, mechanics, and even the way we move through them. For him, this process did not only enrich his understanding but also led to the development of his first book, *Drawing Basics and Video Game Art*. Have you ever wondered what Michelangelo and Mario have in common?

Embodiment and empathy

One of the key ideas that Solarski shared with us was the concept of embodiment, whereby players of video games experience the illusion that something in the game is part of their body, or vice versa.

When asked how this capacity for imagination could be developed within EPIC-WE, Solarski described a workshop in which participants were asked to draw their signatures as large as possible on a sheet of paper and then swap with someone else to trace their signature. Through this exercise, people began to recognise differences in movement, identifying what felt fluid or tense, familiar or strange. It became clear that design is not just visual, but something that is felt. Furthermore, Solarski shared his thoughts with us on the role of empathy. According to Solarski, "when we talk about empathy-driven design, it's not just about fostering positive emotions – it's about truly understanding and connecting with the diverse realities of others, including those in the context of disability, gender identity, and other lived experiences. This is also where games stand out as an art form. They have a unique capacity to allow us to embody not only a wide variety of people but also objects".

"One idea was to take an ordinary game, such as table tennis, and play it with a completely different object, such as a basketball. This way, the game breaks, and players need to adapt and start thinking creatively."

Shaping culture through games

Interview with Annakaisa Kultima

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

Scholar in Game Studies and long-time game jam organiser. Annakaisa has taken part in over 60 game jams—as participant, creator, judge, and organiser. Combining research with practice, she shapes EPIC-WE’s approach to creativity, learning, and cultural exploration.

A living culture of game jams

“One of my first rules for organising a game jam,” Annakaisa shares, “is to understand the local culture of game jams. Expectations vary depending on history, geography, and who’s participating.” EPIC-WE’s mission is to empower youth to explore European values and heritage through games, but “there’s no one-size-fits-all model—especially when it comes to Cultural Game Jams.” Game jams are, she explains, “a living culture,” shaped by context and collaboration. “Some jams are competitive, some are reflective, some prioritise polished products, others focus on the learning process.”

Managing expectations through process

Institutions often use game jams to explore topics like health or heritage. But Annakaisa stresses the need to align goals: “Are we aiming for polished, playable games—or are we creating a space for participatory design, where learning and engagement come first?”

Creativity needs care

Annakaisa advocates for safe, collaborative environments. “Collaboration beats competition,” she says. Mid-jam presentations help: “Participants are often anxious on day one. If you create a space where helping each other is the norm, creativity flourishes.”

Game-making is for everyone

A core belief in Annakaisa’s work is that anyone can contribute to game-making—no matter their background or skillset. Whether you are a poet, historian, or teenager with no coding experience, accessible tools like Bitsy or Twine allow anyone to jump in and create. “There’s still a myth that you need a programmer and an artist to make a game,” she says. “It’s just not true anymore. Game creation is a powerful, democratic medium—and the barriers to entry are lower than ever.”

“The game doesn’t have to be perfect. The impact lies in the experience—the collaboration, the conversation, the connection.”

THE EPIC-WE PROJECT

EPIC-WE is an acronym for ‘Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments’

A Horizon Europe project focusing on youth imagining, creating and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making.

The heart of the project

At its heart, EPIC-WE shows that games are not only entertainment and cultural heritage is not stagnant or dead – when cultural worlds and experiences are brought to life through young people’s imagination, game-making, and cross-sector collaboration both culture and games benefits and become engaging and empowering in new ways.

Game-making as culture-making

EPIC-WE develops, tests, evaluates and delivers a Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub model that brings Higher Education, Cultural Heritage, Creative Industries and Youth (15–25) together as equal partners in culture and games. The model comes to life through Cultural Game Jams - intensive, structured game-making events facilitated by the Cultural Hub partners and where young people co-create and transform heritage, narratives, and values into games through and for culture. Creating and showcasing their games, young people are invited to redefine cultural identity, values, engagement, and experiences and show how games can play a role in co-creating new futures in the intersection of games, heritage, values, and culture.

More than a project

EPIC-WE has not just been a project; it has been a journey empowering young people to shape European culture and futures in games, reframing games as cultural artefacts and game-making as civic participation; it operationalises participatory and co-creative cross-sector collaboration and delivers transferable and open available models, methods, tools, and resources. With the creation of ‘games through culture’ and ‘games for culture,’ games become culture themselves, vehicles for youths’ empowered participation in culture, and carrying the potential to engage new voices and include new identities in shaping European futures in games and culture.

What the project does

The EPIC-WE project is transforming how European culture is created, shared and preserved across Europe and beyond.

1. Unleashing the next generation of culture-makers transforming them from audiences to engaged game-makers.
2. Cultural Game Jams as immersive living laboratories for games and culture using Cultural Game Jam Kits for participatory heritage game creation.
3. Meeting in the middle in QH Cultural Hubs and cross-sector partnerships that break sectoral silos and spark cross-sector collaboration and innovation.
4. Turning culture into playable worlds and experiences that reimagine collections, archives, sites, and artifacts as game-making material.
5. Empowering participation by giving youth the steering wheel in cultural innovation positioning them as fundamental actors in the cultural innovation ecosystem

EPIC-WE shows cross-sector collaboration around game-making as culture-making can generate games and models for engaging heritage; its Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams equip young people with cultural-creative competencies, renew institutional practices in games and culture, and – when partners meet each other in the middle to form an epic we - turn culture into a playground where innovation, heritage and imagination empower each other and youth actively transform, co-shape and give voice to the cultural heritage narratives, values and identities we are all part of.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

WHAT IS A CULTURAL GAME JAM?

Cultural Game Jams aim to foster empowered cultural participation, collaboration, and a sense of belonging in culture by engaging young people in game-making as a form of culture-making.

Step inside the Cultural Game Jam: Where games meet culture

Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) empower young people (ages 15–25) as co-creators of culture through game-making processes as a form of culture-making. They blend traditional game jams with cultural imagination and reflection on heritage sites, archives, artifacts, themes, and values. CGJs position games as a key form of culture-making, inviting participants to reimagine, remix, and reconfigure cultural sites, artifacts, and narratives.

The core elements: A Cultural Game Jam Kit for cultural transformation

In EPIC-WE, participants created over 100 Cultural Game Prototypes, all published on the EPIC-WE Resource Site. Using the CGJ framework and CGJ Kit, these prototypes were refined through the project's 12 CGJs. Some of these Games through/for Culture are showcased in the EPIC-WE Games EXPO Catalogue.

The CGJ framework has four phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, Create (EPIC) and focuses on cultural Worlds and Empowerment (WE). CGJ Kit's methods, tools, team roles, EU value cards, and facilitation guides structure the journey. Specialized methods for engaging culture, games, and values, along with transition tools (Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, Game Logs),

help teams refine ideas, practice cultural imagination, and integrate feedback as they move toward prototyping and creating their Games through/for Culture.

Through the CGJ framework, participants explore cultural heritage for inspiration, shape ideas through sketches and mock-ups, then prototype and playtest. Each CGJ concludes with the participants showcasing their Games through/for Culture to audiences at an EPIC-WE Games EXPO.

Cultural Game Jams: Transforming audiences into culture-makers and game-makers

CGJs provide deep, multidimensional value across sectors. In culture, they transform audiences into engaged co-creators, strengthening heritage and values and highlighting games as cultural form of expression.

Access the Resource Site
<https://lnk.dk/1326>

In education and youth empowerment, CGJs act as real-world living labs, developing vital skills (collaborative, cultural, creative, technical) and fostering cultural agency, voice, and belonging. The format cultivates an “epic we” – a collective, non-hierarchical space where different participants from different sectors and disciplines collaborate across heritage, culture, and games. In this space, youth express cultural viewpoints and identities and show agency in reimagining culture and games.

The EPIC-WE project results show that Cultural Game Jams hold significant promise at the intersection of cultural heritage and game-making. Key potentials include:

Bridging culture & games: CGJs break down the dichotomy between “culture” and “games,” promoting recognition that games are cultural artifacts in themselves and that cultural game-making fosters meaning, identity, and heritage. This encourages youth to see game-making not merely as entertainment but as part of cultural and societal imagination and participation.

Heritage engagement reinterpreted: Cultural institutions often struggle to engage youth. Cultural Game Jams turn tangible and intangible heritage into game-making material for creative reimagining, rather than static artifacts. Youth remix, narrate, critique, and extend heritage creatively, producing new narratives as Games through/for Culture that connect past, present, and future.

Institutional and industry innovation:

Cultural Game Jams serve as innovation spaces for cultural institutions and creative industries. They act as cross-sector hubs and labs for participatory, co-creative approaches to culture and game-making, enabling organisations to work together and to explore new formats and methods. They also act as experimental sites, supporting talent development, fostering experimentation with value-sensitive, heritage-based game worlds, and opening pathways for culturally and socially engaged game-making. These efforts strengthen institutional and industry innovation, expand educational and industry pipelines, and cultivate a new generation of game-makers shaping culture through games.

Cultural Game Jams are not niche experiments but proven, versatile methods for transforming heritage, education, and creative industries into active, co-creative ecosystems. They reshape relationships from passive consumption to partnership, remaking culture with youth rather than just presenting it. Anyone interested in meaningful participation, future-facing cultural practice, or imaginative learning are invited to adopt Cultural Game Jams. Doing so helps organisations find new ways to interpret the past and cultivate the creative capabilities that will define our cultural futures.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

Level completed!

Achievement unlocked: Games for Culture

...but the journey continues!

Explore the next level with the Games
through Culture EXPO Catalogue